

EDITION OF ONE – WORKING PAPERS

The following working papers were written during the six-month period following the successful defense of the ZRC SAZU PhD project, “Works for Works: ‘No Rights’” (2021-2024) ... They represent the transition from the PhD to the post-doctoral project, Edition of One (EO1), a literary agency for collectively produced works of literary-artistic scholarship. Using primarily Medium and Substack, two publishing platforms associated with the shift from Web 2.0 to Web 3.0, to justify and report on the intentions of the literary agency, as of November 2024 the publications’ agenda of the EO1 project will shift to bespoke research projects developed via workshops and scriptoria.

To support the EO1 agenda financially and logistically, please subscribe (monthly or yearly) to the Substack reports, via one of the links below. To support the agenda morally and spiritually, please climb “aboard” by joining the “W(h)ither the Avant-garde?” project – i.e., the first bespoke EO1 research project scheduled for 2025. Updates will continue to be posted to Substack, but the research dossier associated with the project will be distributed in Peer-to-Peer (P2P) or samizdat fashion and editioned beyond the auspices of Web 2.0, as Web 2.0 times out, and selectively by way of the auspices of Web 3.0, as Web 3.0 begins to truly replace Web 2.0. As for Education 4.0, the EO1 project will only ever engage with such practices through de facto critique and through creative disruption toward de-colonizing academia and freeing scholars (and artist-scholars) from enslavement to Capital.

“Pivot + Walk Away?” *Substack* (November 23, 2024)

<https://editionofone.substack.com/p/pivot-walk-away>

“À bientôt,” *Medium* (November 17, 2024)

<https://medium.com/@agencex/%C3%A0-bient%C3%B4t-db14f34cdee4>

“The Future Now,” *Substack* (November 17, 2024)

<https://editionofone.substack.com/p/the-future-now>

“New York, New York, New York,” *Medium* (November 14, 2024)

<https://medium.com/@agencex/new-york-new-york-new-york-18cd174353d2>

“Return to the USSA,” *Substack* (November 10, 2024)

<https://editionofone.substack.com/p/return-to-the-ussa>

“IPR + Serfdom,” *Medium* (November 5, 2024)

<https://medium.com/@agencex/ipr-serfdom-501a8b8f2c0a>

“End of the Road,” *Substack* (November 2, 2024)

<https://editionofone.substack.com/p/end-of-the-road>

“Prelude to Exile,” *Substack* (October 30, 2024)

<https://editionofone.substack.com/p/prelude-to-exile>

“Totally Useless Collegia,” *Substack* (October 27, 2024)

<https://editionofone.substack.com/p/totally-useless-collegia>

“Revolution @ SOAS,” *Substack* (October 24, 2024)

<https://editionofone.substack.com/p/revolution-at-soas>

“Eleven Days in Ljubljana,” *Substack* (October 22, 2024)

<https://editionofone.substack.com/p/eleven-days-in-ljubljana>

“Franciscan Red Thread,” *Substack* (October 20, 2024)

<https://editionofone.substack.com/p/franciscan-red-thread>

“Green Light,” *Substack* (October 14, 2024)

<https://editionofone.substack.com/p/green-light>

“JFK-LHR-VCE,” *Substack* (October 11, 2024)

<https://editionofone.substack.com/p/jfk-lhr-vce>

“EO1 Ecosystem – Dogma 24,” *Substack* (October 1, 2024)

<https://editionofone.substack.com/p/eo1-ecosystem-dogma-24>

“Cover Story,” *Substack* (September 25, 2024)

<https://editionofone.substack.com/p/cover-story>

“The Catasterism,” *Substack* (September 13, 2024)

<https://editionofone.substack.com/p/the-catasterism>

“Forget IPR (+ OA + CC),” *Substack* (September 6, 2024)

<https://editionofone.substack.com/p/forget-ipr-oa-cc>

“Venice Time-machine,” *Substack* (September 5, 2024)

<https://editionofone.substack.com/p/venice-time-machine>

“The Sublime of the NFT,” *Substack* (September 2, 2024)

<https://editionofone.substack.com/p/the-sublime-of-the-nft>

“Edition of One Prospectus,” *Zenodo* (August 29, 2024)

<https://zenodo.org/records/13483665>

“Academic Lettrism – The Divine Comedy,” *Substack* (August 16, 2024)

<https://editionofone.substack.com/p/academic-lettrism>

“Auto-hagiography,” *Substack* (August 15, 2024)

<https://editionofone.substack.com/p/auto-hagiography>

“The Wind,” *Substack* (August 14, 2024)

<https://editionofone.substack.com/p/the-wind>

“My ‘Brilliant Career,’” *Medium* (August 12, 2024)

<https://medium.com/@agencex/my-brilliant-career-aa3868509e05>

“The Back Foot,” *Substack* (August 11, 2024)

<https://editionofone.substack.com/p/the-back-foot>

“The Romance of AI?” *Substack* (August 10, 2024)

<https://editionofone.substack.com/p/the-romance-of-ai>

“Forms of Peer Review,” *Substack* (August 9, 2024)

<https://editionofone.substack.com/p/forms-of-peer-review>

“The Author Disappears,” *Substack* (August 7, 2024)

<https://editionofone.substack.com/p/the-author-disappears>

“Fate + Grace,” *Substack* (August 4, 2024)

<https://editionofone.substack.com/p/fate-grace>

“The Hydra,” *Medium* (June 24, 2024)

<https://medium.com/@agencex/the-hydra-cac25378ae9f>

“EO1 Draft Protocols,” *Zenodo* (June 21, 2024)

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12205953>

[...]

For posts to Zenodo regarding the “Works for Works: ‘No Rights’ project, please see the following link ...

<https://zenodo.org/communities/w4w2>